

Fermat's Last Theorem : 17 century proof

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Abstract

If $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$ has ordered pair solution of natural number (X, Y, Z) , (n is a prime number)

First, if $n \nmid Y$, ordered pair (X, Y, Z) must satisfy the following three conditions:

① $(X, Y, Z) = (RA, Z - R^n, Z)$, where $\gcd(R, n) = 1$, $\gcd(R, A) = 1$, $\gcd(R, Z) = 1$, $\gcd(A, Z) = 1$, $\gcd(A, n) = 1$

then this equation form is bound to be accompanied by a contradiction.

② If $n \mid Y$, we can prove that it is impossible.

③ The natural number Y is either a multiple of n or not a multiple of n .

By ①, $n \nmid Y$ is impossible.

By ②, $n \mid Y$ is impossible.

Therefore, the natural number ordered pair (X, Y, Z) cannot exist.

Introduction

There are infinitely many coprime natural number solutions to the Pythagorean equation for $n=2$.

However, for exponents greater than $n=3$, it is impossible to find an ordered pair of natural numbers that satisfies the equation. I was curious about the reason for it, and to prove this theorem, I derived (①, ②, ③)

Fermat's little theorem is used in this proof.

The table contents of this paper

Chapter 0. Lemma

Chapter 1. $(X, Y, Z) = (RA, Z - R^n, Z)$ (about ①)

Chapter 2. If Y is a multiple of n , it is impossible.

Therefore ordered pair (X, Y, Z) cannot exist.

Chapter 0. Lemma

Chapter 0. Lemma

Lemma1. If there exists an ordered pair of natural numbers (x,y,z) , then there exists a coprime ordered pair of natural numbers (x,y,z) .

Infinite natural numbers with infinite 0s, such as $10000\dots$, are not treated as natural numbers. Why is that? Because the following question cannot be answered.

Is $10000\dots$ a multiple of 3?

If an infinite natural number like $10000\dots$ is divided by 3, the quotient is infinite. Since it is infinitely divisible, there is no such thing as a remainder. Therefore, there is no chance of a decimal point. Does that mean that $10000\dots$ is a multiple of 3? We may say yes.

However, it can be proven that 10^n , a power of 10, is not divisible by 3. This is because 10 and 3 are coprime, and no power of 10 can produce a factor of 3.

This is contradiction. It means that $10000\dots$ is not a normal natural number.

In fact, Fermat proved the case of $n = 4$ by the method of infinite descent. If there is an ordered pair of natural numbers satisfying the case of $n = 4$, then the ordered pair of natural numbers must be an infinitely small natural number, which was a contradiction.

So an ordered pair of natural numbers (x,y,z) has finite common divisor. So we can find a coprime ordered pair of natural numbers (x,y,z)

Lemma 2.

If $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$ has a coprime natural number ordered pair (x,y,z) , it is impossible for only two of the three numbers to have common divisors.

pf) If X and Y has common divisor A and Z is coprime to A,

$$X=Ax$$

$$Y=Ay$$

$$Z=Z$$

If you substitute it into the equation $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$,

$$A^n x^n + A^n Y^n = Z^n$$

$$A^n (x^n + y^n) = Z^n$$

$$x^n + y^n = \left(\frac{Z}{A}\right)^n$$

Since the left side is a natural number, the right side must also be a natural number.

But Z and A is coprime, which is contradiction.

The case where only Y and Z have a common divisor B can be proven in a similar way. (X,By,Bz)

$$X^n = B^n (z^n - y^n)$$

X and B is coprime. It is impossible.

Lemma 3. For r such that $0 < r < n$, nCr is a multiple of n . (n is a prime number, which is a index of Fermat equation)

pf) nCr is a natural number. In Pascal's triangle, we can inductively prove that these numbers are natural numbers.

$$nCr = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{(n-r)!r!}$$

But $(n-r)$, $(n-r-1)$, $(n-r-2)$, ... 2 , 1 can't divide n because n is a prime number and $n-r < n$.

Similarly, r , $(r-1)$, $(r-2)$, $(r-3)$, ..., 2 , 1 can't divide n so the denominator always has n . Thus, nCr is always a natural number that is a multiple of n .

Lemma 4. For any two natural numbers a and b ,

$(a + b)^p \equiv a^p + b^p \pmod{p}$, (where p is a prime number)

pf)

$$\begin{aligned} & (a + b)^p \\ &= a^p + \binom{p}{1} a^{p-1} b + \binom{p}{2} a^{p-2} b^2 + \dots + \binom{p}{p-2} a^2 b^{p-2} \\ &+ \binom{p}{1} a b^{p-1} + b^p \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 3, any $\binom{p}{r}$ ($1 \leq r \leq p - 1$) is a multiple of p .

Thus the remainder of dividing the left side by p is the same as the remainder when $a^p + b^p$ is divided by p .

$$\therefore (a + b)^p \equiv a^p + b^p \pmod{p}$$

Lemma 5. Fermat's little theorem(1)

If p is a prime number, then for any integer a ,

the number $a^p - a$ is an integer multiple of p . In the notation of modular arithmetic, this is expressed as

$$a^p \equiv a \pmod{p}$$

pf) By Lemma 4, $(a + b)^p \equiv a^p + b^p$

when $a=1, b=1, 2^p \equiv 1 + 1 \equiv 2$

$a=2, b=1, 3^p \equiv 2^p + 1 \equiv 3 \quad (\because 2^p \equiv 2)$

$a=3, b=1, 4^p \equiv 3^p + 1 \equiv 4 \quad (\because 3^p \equiv 3)$

assuming $n^p \equiv n \pmod{p}$,

$$(n + 1)^p \equiv n^p + 1 \equiv n + 1 \pmod{p}$$

It is inductively derived that $(n + 1)^p \equiv n + 1 \pmod{p}$

Thus $a^p \equiv a \pmod{p}$.

Lemma 6. Fermat's little theorem(2)

If a is coprime to p , then Fermat's little theorem is equivalent to the statement that $a^{p-1} - 1$ is an integer multiple of p .
in symbols:

$$a^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$$

pf)

by Lemma 5, $a^p \equiv a \pmod{p}$.

Then a^p is represented as $a^p = pK + a$, where K is a proper natural number.

Since the left side is a multiple of a , the right side is also a multiple of a .

But since $\gcd(a,p)=1$, K must be a multiple of a .

So we can represent $K=ak$, for any suitable natural number k .

$$a^p = pak + a$$

If we divide both sides by a , $a^{p-1} = pk + 1$,

That is, $a^{p-1} \equiv 1$

Lemma7. The following equation is a contradiction:

$$p^2N = pK$$

where p is prime number, N is coprime to p , and K is coprime to p .

Because if you divide both sides by p , you get

$$pN = K$$

The left side is a multiple of p . But the right side is not a multiple of p .

This Lemma will play a very important role in the proof in chapters 2 and 3.

Lemma 8. There is no natural number solution satisfying the following equation.

$$x^4 + y^4 = z^4$$

This is the case when the exponent $n=4$
Since it was proven by Fermat, I omit the proof.

But we must recognize one fact.

If there is no ordered pair (x,y,z) of natural numbers satisfying $x^4 + y^4 = z^4$,

then there is no ordered pair (x,y,z) of natural numbers satisfying $x^8 + y^8 = z^8$.

pf) Let's prove it by reductio ad absurdum.

Let's assume that there is no natural number solution when $n=4$, but there is a natural number solution when $n=8$.
And let $x^2 = X, y^2 = Y, z^2 = Z$.

Then we substitute this into $x^8 + y^8 = z^8$ ($n=4$)

$$(x^2)^4 + (y^2)^4 = (z^2)^4$$

$$X^4 + Y^4 = Z^4$$

It is another equation with exponent $n=4$, which is contradiction. So we can see that if there is no solution when $n=4$, there is no solution when $n=8$.

Similarly, there is no natural number solution with exponent $n=4,8,12,16,20...$

Lemma9. If there is no natural number solution for prime exponents greater than or equal to 3, then there is no natural number solution for all natural exponents greater than or equal to 3.

pf)
By Lemma8, there are no natural number solutions when the exponent n is a multiple of 4.

And all natural numbers greater than or equal to 3 are either prime or divisible by prime numbers.

If we prove it for the case $n=3$, there is no solution for $n=6,9,12,15\dots$

If we prove it for the case $n=5$, there is no solution for $n=10,15,20,25\dots$

All natural numbers that are not powers of 2 are either prime numbers greater than or equal to 3 or are divisible by prime numbers greater than or equal to 3.

Therefore, if we prove this for prime exponents greater than or equal to 3, then there are no natural number solutions for all natural exponents greater than or equal to 3.

Therefore, this paper will only prove the case where the exponent n is a prime number greater than or equal to 3.

Lemma 10. $p \mid Y^n$ is equivalent to $p \mid Y$

(p is a prime number. And $p \mid Y^n$ means Y^n is a multiple of p .)

pf)

p is a prime number. so Y must have p as a prime factor. Let's assume that Y does not have p as a prime factor. Then p cannot be generated by raising Y to a power.

'Because p is a prime number.'

Lemma11. The following ordered pair forms cannot satisfy the Fermat equation.

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{n-1}, ny, Z)$$

I proved this in this paper- chapter1.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15275524>

Lemma12. (generalization) The following ordered pair forms cannot satisfy the Fermat equation.

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{kn-1}R^n, nRy, Z)$$

It is also proved in this paper, chapter2.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15275524>

(Same as the link above.)

Lemma13. In an ordered pair (X,Y,Z) that satisfies Fermat equation,

Y is a multiple of n if and only if (Z-X) is a multiple of n.

(=>) In $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$, Since Y is a multiple of n,

$$X^n \equiv Z^n \pmod{n}$$

And by Fermat's little theorem (Lemma6),

$$X \equiv Z \pmod{n}$$

Therefore (Z-X) is a multiple of n.

(<=)

$$\begin{aligned} Y^n &= Z^n - X^n \\ &= (Z - X) \times \{Z^{n-1} + Z^{n-2}X + \dots + ZX^{n-2} + X^{n-1}\} \end{aligned}$$

Since (Z-X) is a multiple of n, the left-hand side must be a multiple of n.

Therefore Y is a multiple of n.

[Definition1]

Let

$$\begin{aligned} &\Phi_n(Z, X) \\ &= (Z^{n-1} + Z^{n-2}X + Z^{n-3}X^2 \dots + Z^2X^{n-3} + ZX^{n-2} + X^{n-1}) \end{aligned}$$

Chapter 1.

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, Y, Z)$$

(n is a prime number greater
than or equal to 3,
and $n \nmid XY$)

plus: X,Y can exchange each other. So if we prove about X, then Y is also proved.

Chapter 1.

$$\boxed{X^n + Y^n = Z^n}$$

Let's call it 'Fermat equation'.

(n is a prime number, and X,Y,Z is coprime each other. By Lemma 1 and 2, we can choose coprime ordered pair (X,Y,Z))

Chapter 1-1

First, let's show that

$X=Z-p$ is impossible. p is any prime number and coprime to n.

That is, the difference between Z and X cannot be a prime number p.

pf)

$$\boxed{(X, Y, Z) = (Z - p, Y, Z) \text{ ----- } \text{---} (\mathbb{A})}$$

Substitute this ordered pair into the Fermat equation.

$$(Z - p)^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

expand it.

$$\begin{aligned} Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-2} \\ + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-1} - p^n + Y^n = Z^n \end{aligned}$$

Note that n is a 'prime number' greater than or equal to 3. Since Z^n is common to both sides, subtract it and eliminate it.

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-2} \\
& + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-1} - p^n + Y^n = 0 \text{ ----- } \text{---(B)}
\end{aligned}$$

Let's move everything to the right side, leaving only Y^n on the left side.

$$\begin{aligned}
& Y^n \\
& = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p - \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^2 + \dots + \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-2} \\
& - \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-1} + p^n
\end{aligned}$$

Since all terms on the right side have 'p' in common, they are grouped by p.

$$\begin{aligned}
& = p \left\{ \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} - \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p + \dots + \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-3} \right. \\
& \left. - \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-2} + p^{n-1} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$Y^n = p \times K$$

where K is a proper natural number.

Anyway, the right side is a multiple of p, so Y^n is a multiple of p. Since p is a prime number,

$$p \mid Y^n$$

means

$$p \mid Y$$

by Lemma10.

Since $p \mid Y$,

let $Y = py$ for a suitable natural number y .

and substitute it into (B)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-2} \\
 & + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-1} - p^n + (py)^n = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

$\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p = nZ^{n-1} p$. Let's move this term to the right-hand side.

And divide both sides by p . Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-3} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-2} - p^{n-1} \\
 & + p^{n-1} y^n = nZ^{n-1}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since all terms on the left-hand side have p as a factor, the left-hand side is a multiple of p .

$$\begin{aligned}
 & p \\
 & \times \left\{ \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-4} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-3} - p^{n-2} \right. \\
 & \left. + p^{n-2} y^n \right\} = nZ^{n-1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$p \times N = nZ^{n-1}$$

N is a suitable natural number. Since left-hand side is a multiple of p , the right-hand side is also a multiple of p .

$$p \times N = nZ^{n-1}$$

Since p is a prime number, only two cases are possible.

i) $p \mid n$

ii) $p \mid Z^{n-1}$

Let's see. ii) means $p \mid Z$. (\because Lemma 10.)

And ii) is impossible. Why?

$$(A) - \boxed{(X, Y, Z) = (Z - p, Y, Z)}$$

Since $p \mid Z$, let $Z = pz$ for the suitable natural number z .

Then $(X, Y, Z) = (pz - p, Y, pz)$

Look. $X = pz - p = p(z - 1) \rightarrow X$ is a multiple of p .

and Z is a multiple of p . (p is a prime number, so $p \geq 2$)

There is a common prime factor p between X and Z .

It is a contradiction by Lemma 2. If X and Z have a common prime factor p , then Y also has a common prime factor p by Lemma 2.

(X, Y, Z) have a common prime factor p .

We were looking for ordered pairs (X, Y, Z) that are coprime.

So this is a contradiction and case ii) is impossible.

How about case i)?

case i) is impossible because it means $(Z-X)$ is a multiple of n .
And it forces Y to be a multiple of n . (by Lemma 14)

But we assumed that $n \nmid XY$.

So the case i) is impossible.

In summary, if $X=Z-p$, only the following two cases were possible.

i) $p \mid n$

ii) $p \mid Z^{n-1}$

But we have so far shown that both of these cases are impossible.

Therefore, $X=Z-p$ is impossible.

There is never a case where X and Z differ by some arbitrary prime number p .

In chapter 1, I will continue to chain together this type of development. The end of this chain will be

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, Y, Z)$$

I will omit detailed explanations as long as the logic is similar to the previous proof(Chapter 1-1).

Chapter 1-2

$$X = Z - p_1 p_2 p_3 \cdots p_k$$

is impossible.

It means that the difference between Z and X cannot be the product of the first powers of prime numbers.

For example, Z=19, X=13 is impossible.

Because $Z - X = 6 = 2 \times 3$

If we express this as an ordered pair,

$$\boxed{(X, Y, Z) = (Z - p_1 p_2 p_3 \cdots p_k, Y, Z)} \text{-----} (\mathbb{D})$$

Let's prove it as in 1-1.

Absurdity - Assuming that the above ordered pair (\mathbb{D}) is possible.

Let's replace P with

$$P = p_1 p_2 p_3 \cdots p_k$$

$$X = Z - P$$

$$Y = Y$$

$$Z = Z$$

Substitute this into 'Fermat equation'.

Remember that it comes out similar to 1-1

$$(Z - P)^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} P + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} P^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 P^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z P^{n-1} - P^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Y^n = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} P - \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} P^2 + \dots + \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 P^{n-2} - \binom{n}{n-1} Z P^{n-1} + P^n$$

$P \mid Y^n$ and $P \mid Y$ (\because Lemma10.)

' $Y=Py$ '

$$P^n y^n + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} P^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 P^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z P^{n-1} - P^n = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} P$$

$$P \times M = nZ^{n-1}$$

n is a single prime number.

But $P = p_1 p_2 p_3 \dots p_k$ is not.

Therefore, the possible case i) is when n is equal to a single prime factor p_i of P , and Z contains all remaining factors of P .

For example, $P = 3 \times 5 \times 11$, and $n = 5$ and $3 \times 11 \mid Z$

The other case ii) is $n \nmid P$.

Therefore Z contains P . $P \mid Z^n$ and $P \mid Z$.

Whether it's i) or ii), a contradiction arises. Let's see.

i) and ii) means Z contains at least one p_i , which is the prime factors of $P = p_1 p_2 p_3 \cdots p_k$. $(1 \leq i \leq k)$

Since p_i is a prime number, it is obvious that $p_i \geq 2$.

Let $Z = p_i z$ for some suitable natural number z .

And let $P = p_i q$, where $q = \frac{P}{p_i}$

It is already contradiction. Why?

$$X = Z - P = p_i z - p_i q = p_i (z - q)$$

$Y = P y$, it is a multiple of p_i

$$Z = p_i z$$

We can see that the ordered pair (X, Y, Z) has a common prime factor p_i .

It is contradiction because we assumed that X, Y, Z is coprime each other!

So we have checked that the cases

$$X=Z-p,$$

$$X=Z-p_1p_2p_3 \cdots p_k$$

is impossible.

How about this?

$$X = Z - p_1p_2^2p_3^2 \cdots p_k^2$$

It means the difference between Z and X is expressed by 1st square prime factor p_1 , and the others are prime with multi powers.

For example, Z= 463, X=13

$$Z - X = 450 = 2 \times 3^2 \times 5^2$$

Is it possible?

The difference between Z and X is

$$Z - X = p_1p_2^2p_3^2 \cdots p_k^2$$

$$\text{Let } Q = \frac{Z-X}{p_1}.$$

Then $Z - X = p_1 \times Q$ for coprime p_1 and Q .

$$X=Z - p_1 Q \quad (\gcd(p_1, Q) = 1)$$

$$Y=Y$$

$$Z=Z$$

Substitute this into the 'Fermat equation'

$$\begin{aligned} & Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p_1 Q + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p_1^2 Q^2 - \dots \\ & - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p_1^{n-2} Q^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p_1^{n-1} Q^{n-1} - p_1^n Q^n + Y^n \\ & = Z^n \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & Y^n \\ & = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p_1 Q - \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p_1^2 Q^2 + \dots + \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p_1^{n-2} Q^{n-2} \\ & - \binom{n}{n-1} Z p_1^{n-1} Q^{n-1} + p_1^n Q^n \end{aligned}$$

$$Y^n = p_1 \times K$$

Y is a multiple of p_1 . So let $Y = p_1 y$. Substitute it into the equation above.

$$\begin{aligned} & p_1^n y^n + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p_1^2 Q^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p_1^{n-2} Q^{n-2} \\ & + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p_1^{n-1} Q^{n-1} - p_1^n Q^n = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p_1 Q \end{aligned}$$

Divide both sides by p_1 . Then

$$p_1 \times K = n Z^{n-1} Q$$

$$p_1 \times K = nZ^{n-1}Q$$

p_1 is coprime to Q . Therefore two cases:
 $n = p_1$ or $p_1 \mid Z^{n-1}$

But $p_1 \mid Z^{n-1}$ is impossible. Because it means $p_1 \mid Z$.

In previous page,

$$X = Z - p_1Q = p_1z - p_1Q = p_1(z - Q)$$

$$Y = Y$$

$$Z = Z = p_1z$$

X and Z is not coprime. So it is contradiction.

How about $p_1 = n$?

$$X = Z - nQ. \text{ (n is coprime to Q still.)}$$

$$Y = Y$$

$$Z = Z$$

Substitute this ordered pair (X, Y, Z) to the 'Fermat equation'.

$$(Z - nQ)^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} nQ + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} n^2 Q^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 n^{n-2} Q^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z n^{n-1} Q^{n-1} - n^n Q^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Y^n = n \times K$$

Let $Y=ny$ and substitute it to the above equation.

$$y^n n^n + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} n^2 Q^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 n^{n-2} Q^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z n^{n-1} Q^{n-1} - n^n Q^n = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} nQ$$

Divide both sides by n^2 . And the left-hand side is a multiple of n .

$$n \times K = Z^{n-1} Q$$

n and Q are coprime. So Z is a multiple of n , which is a contradiction. We let $Z=nz$

$$X=Z-nQ=nz-nQ=n(z-Q)$$

$$Y=Y$$

$$Z=nZ$$

X and Z are not coprime. So it is a contradiction.

Therefore,

$$Z - X = p_1 \times Q$$

(p_1 and Q are coprime)

all case of this form is impossible. For example,

$$Z - X = p_1 p_2 p_3^2 p_4^6$$

$$Z - X = p_1 p_2^7 p_3^{61}$$

$$Z - X = p_1 p_2^2 p_3^2 p_4^2 p_5^{1557} p_6^{564226}$$

⋮

These are all included in case above,

$$Z - X = p_1 \times Q$$

Now, let's check whether $X = Z - p^2$ is possible.

The logic used is pretty much the same as what we've been using so far in Chapter 1-1, 1-2

Next Chapter 1-3,

I'll prove that $X = Z - p^2$ is impossible, and additionally I will prove

$$X = Z - p^2 \times Q$$

is impossible. (p and Q is coprime)

Chapter 1-3

Let's assume that exists the following disjoint ordered pair
(X,Y,Z)

$$X=Z - p^2$$

$$Y=Y$$

$$Z=Z$$

$$(Z - p^2)^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p^2 + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 (p^2)^{n-2} \\ + \binom{n}{n-1} Z (p^2)^{n-1} - p^{2n} + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Y^n = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-1} Z (p^2)^{n-1} + p^{2n}$$

$$Y^n = p^2 \times K$$

We can know Y^n is a multiple of p^2

But... can we say Y is a multiple of p^2 ?

No. Counter example)

$$p=5 \text{ and } p^2 = 25, n=3. Y=5 \times 3$$

Y is not a multiple of 25, but $Y^3 = 5^3 \times 3^3$ is a multiple of 125.

So all we know for sure is that Y is a multiple of p.

Let $Y=py$. Then

$$X=Z - p^2$$

$$Y=py$$

$$Z=Z$$

$$p^n y^n + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^4 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 (p^2)^{n-2} \\ + \binom{n}{n-1} Z (p^2)^{n-1} - p^{2n} = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p^2$$

Divide both sides by p^2 .

$$p^{n-2} y^n + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{2n-4} - p^{2n-2} = n Z^{n-1}$$

Since n is greater than or equal to 3,

The left-hand side is a multiple of p .

So

i) $n=p$

ii) $p \mid Z$

But ii) is impossible. Because $Z=pz$ means X and Z have a common divisor p . Look at the form of the ordered pair above.

But!

i) is impossible. Because it forces Y to be a multiple of n .

ii) is also impossible. Because it means that Z and Y are multiples of p at the same time.

Therefore $(Z-Y) = p^2$ is impossible.

In a similar way, we can show that $(Z - X) = p^2 \times Q$ is also impossible. (Q is coprime to p^2).

How about this?

$$(Z - X) = p^3$$

If $n=3$, no contradiction is induced by the method of Lemma7.

But if $n=5,7,11,13...$

This still leads to a contradiction by Lemma7.

Do you see the rule?

In the Fermat equation with exponent n ,

$$(Z - X) = p^n$$

$(Z-X) = n$ -th power is possible and any other exponent causes a contradiction.

How about this?

$$(Z - X) = p^n \times q^{n-2}$$

Since it is not a n -th power, it causes contradiction by Lemma7.

(next page)

$$Y^n = (Z - X) \times \Phi_n(Z, X) \quad (\alpha)$$

If $(Z - X) = p^n \times q^{n-2}$,

Y must be a multiple of pq . Let $Y = pqy$

Then Y^n is a multiple of $p^n q^n$.

This causes contradiction. Since $X = Z - p^n q^{n-2}$, if we expand

$$(Z - p^n q^{n-2})^n + p^n q^n y^n = Z^n$$

Z^n on both sides are canceled and we get a term

$$\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p^n q^{n-2}$$

All terms except this term is a multiple of $p^n q^n$. So by Lemma7, it is contradiction.

In general, if factorization of $(Z - X)$ is

$$(Z - X) = p_1^{r_1} \times p_2^{r_2} \times \dots \times p_m^{r_m}$$

By (α) , Y must have p_i to the

$$\left[\frac{r_i}{n} + 1 \right]$$

for all $1 \leq i \leq m$

$[]$ is the Gaussian symbol. If any r_i is not a multiple of n , the Fermat equation is contradiction by Lemma7.

Therefore $(Z - X)$ must be n -th power.

$$Z - X = R^n$$

$$Y^n = Z^n - X^n = (Z - X) \times \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

Y must be a multiple of R^n . If not, Y^n cannot be a multiple of $(Z - X)$.

$$Y = RA$$

Therefore the ordered pair (X, Y, Z) must be

$$(Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

R is coprime to A . Because if $\gcd(R, A) = g \geq 2$,

$$(Z - R^n)^n + R^n A^n = Z^n$$

Z^n on both sides are canceled and $R^n A^n$ is a multiple of g^{2n} .

all terms except $-\binom{n}{1}Z^{n-1}R^n$ is a multiple of g^{2n} .

So this is contradiction. Therefore $\gcd(R, A) = 1$

Since $Z - X = R^n$, we can let

$$X = xR^n + c$$

$$Z = zR^n + c$$

c is a natural number that satisfy $c < R^n$.

$$X = xR^n + c$$

$$Z = zR^n + c$$

$$Y^n = Z^n - X^n$$

$$= \left\{ (zR)^n + \binom{n}{1} (zR)^{n-1}c + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} zRc^{n-1} + c^n \right\} \\ - \left\{ (xR)^n + \binom{n}{1} (xR)^{n-1}c + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} xRc^{n-1} + c^n \right\}$$

$c^n - c^n$ are canceled and group like terms for c .

Then all terms are multiple of $R^n(z - x)$.

$$Y^n = R^n(z - x) \times (\text{natural number})$$

Since $Y^n = R^n A^n$,

$$A^n = (z - x) \times (f(z, x)) - (\varphi 1)$$

c, n are fixed constant and z, x are variables.

$f(z, x)$ is a natural number.

Thus A^n has $(z - x)$ as a factor.

However,

$$Y^n = R^n A^n = Z^n - X^n = (Z - X) \times \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

Since $(Z - X) = R^n$,

$$A^n = \Phi_n(Z, X) = Z^{n-1} + Z^{n-2}X + \dots + ZX^{n-2} + X^{n-1}$$

Substitute $Z = zR^n + c$, $X = xR^n + c$

$$A^n = \Phi_n(Z, X) = \Phi_n(zR^n + c, xR^n + c) = g(z, x)$$

Since

$$(z - x)f(z, x) = A^n = g(z, x)$$

$$(z - x)f(z, x) = g(z, x)$$

thus $g(z, x)$ has $(z - x)$ as a factor.

Therefore if we substitute $z = x$ into the $g(z, x)$, the value of $g(z, x)$ is 0.

$$\begin{aligned} g(x, x) &= \Phi_n(xR^n + c, xR^n + c) = \Phi_n(X, X) \\ &= \{X^{n-1} + X^{n-1} + \dots + X^{n-1} + X^{n-1}\} \end{aligned}$$

Since the number of the terms in $\Phi_n(Z, X)$ is n ,

$$\begin{aligned} g(x, x) &= \Phi_n(xR^n + c, xR^n + c) = \Phi_n(X, X) = nX^{n-1} \\ &= n(xR^n + c)^{n-1} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore (xR^n + c) = 0$$

$$c = 0, R^n = 0$$

It is contradiction.

c cannot be zero. Because

$$X = xR^n + c$$

if $c = 0$, X is a multiple of R^n .

It is contradiction.

Therefore the ordered pair $(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$ is impossible.

Chapter 2

One of X or Y is a multiple of n .

Note: It is impossible X and Y are multiples of n at the same time. (By Lemma2)

It doesn't matter which of X and Y is a multiple of n .

(X and Y can exchange each other)

Let Y is a multiple of n .

By Lemma12, $(Z - X)$ is a multiple of n .

By using Lemma7 as Chapter1,

$X = Z - n$ is impossible. Because it causes Y to be a multiple of n ,

and it means that Y^n is a multiple of n^n .

But if we expand

$$(Z - n)^n + (ny)^n = Z^n$$

Z^n on both sides are canceled and all terms except

$$- \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} n$$

is a multiples of n^n .

Therefore it is contradiction by Lemma7.

Since $\binom{n}{1}$ is a multiple of n ,

in general, only the following form of X does not cause a contradiction.

$$X = Z - n^{kn-1}$$

At this time, Y is a multiple of n^k .

This is why I proved this form

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{kn-1} R^n, n^k R y, Z)$$

I proved this form is impossible. (Lemma 12)

Therefore, one of X or Y is a multiple of n is impossible.

Y is either a multiple of n or not a multiple of n .

Chapter1) $n \nmid Y$ is impossible.

Chapter2) $n \mid Y$ is impossible.

Therefore, no natural number Y can satisfy the equation.

The same applies if X is a multiple of n .

Conclusion

There is no natural numbers X and Y that satisfy the Fermat equation.

Therefore there is no natural number ordered pair (X, Y, Z) that satisfies the equation

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

So the Fermat's Last Theorem is true.

Thank you for reading.

Reference

Fermat's little theorem

<https://brilliant.org/wiki/fermats-little-theorem/>

Euclidean Algorithm

<https://brilliant.org/wiki/euclidean-algorithm/>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15275524>